

MICROMANAGEMENT LEADERSHIP STYLE AND JOB PERFORMANCE OF GENERATION Z PRODUCTION EMPLOYEES IN ABC CORPORATION

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ABSTRACT

Micromanagement was a widely debated leadership style, particularly when managing Generation Z employees who valued independence and workplace flexibility. This study explored the effects of micromanagement, focusing on managerial control and decision-making autonomy on the job performance of Generation Z production employees at ABC Corporation. It assessed the relationship between micromanagement and work efficiency, productivity, motivation, and engagement. A descriptive correlational research design involved 120 respondents from ABC Corporation's production department. Results showed that micromanagement in terms of managerial control was manifested, with a mean of 2.57 and a standard deviation of 0.984. Decision-making autonomy was also manifested, with a mean of 2.60 and a standard deviation of 0.768. Regarding performance, work efficiency and productivity were rated as Good (mean = 2.61), while employee motivation and engagement were also rated Good (mean = 2.85). Correlation analysis revealed a significant inverse relationship between managerial control and job performance. Higher levels of control were associated with decreased productivity and engagement ($r = -0.189$, $p = 0.039$ for work efficiency/productivity; $r = -0.180$, $p = 0.049$ for motivation/engagement). Meanwhile, decision-making autonomy did not have a statistically significant relationship with productivity or engagement ($r = -0.074$, $p = 0.420$; $r = -0.135$, $p = 0.141$). The proposed action plan focused on improving leadership strategies by balancing control and autonomy. Recommendations included adaptive leadership training, mentoring programs, and flexible work arrangements to boost motivation, innovation, and overall job performance. The study offered insights for enhancing management practices in a modern, evolving workforce.

Keywords: *micromanagement, managerial control, decision-making autonomy, job performance, engagement*

INTRODUCTION

In an era marked by rapid globalization and technological advancement, leadership styles have evolved to meet the changing demands of the modern workforce. Of all these styles, micromanagement has received much attention in the business landscape and organizational studies. Global studies show micromanagement and its presence in different fields and countries, resulting in positive and negative impacts. This leadership style in organizations worldwide continues to be a concern, and complications were even more noticeable in the post-COVID-19 period. While some leaders have always considered micromanaging to keep their subordinates in check or prevent slowdown in productivity, others consider it a complete drawback that denies employees self-responsibility and demoralizes them. The global discussion surrounding micromanagement has been further intensified by the growing influence of Generation Z in the workforce, a cohort characterized by their desire for independence, innovation, and professional development.

As mentioned above, micromanagement of leaders has been prevalent mostly around the globe since the pandemic. As organizations transitioned to hybrid work models, leaders faced the challenge of maintaining productivity while employees worked remotely. In organizations in the UK, for instance, research indicated that micromanagement arises whenever leaders try to exercise authority when direct oversight of employees' work is not achievable due to a virtual or online work setup. Ryan and Cross (2024) also pointed out that micromanagement leadership demotivates workers, decreasing their job satisfaction levels and increasing their tendency to leave the company.

On the other hand, Salsabila et al. (2022) observed that the employees belonging to Generation Z in countries like Indonesia acknowledged the need for micromanagement during the first stages in their working careers, provided that they are inexperienced and need close supervision. These global scenarios of micromanagement showed that this leadership may have advantages and disadvantages in different cultures and organizations.

In the Philippines, trends in micromanagement mirror the global debate, especially in the context of the youngest generation of workers—Generation Z. Similar to many other countries, the Philippine workforce has undergone a dramatic transformation due to the influx of young employees. Once considered a conventional leadership style, Micromanagement is increasingly criticized by Generation Z workers who view it as a barrier to autonomy, innovation, and job satisfaction.

A study by Bautista and Cahingas (2024) reinforced this sentiment, emphasizing that Filipino Gen Z employees are exceptionally resistant to rigid, top-down management

approaches, which they perceived as stifling their growth and individuality. The COVID-19 pandemic further intensified this issue, ushering in new work setups and reshaping employee expectations.

As mentioned by Philcare (2024), 55 percent of Filipino Gen Z workers preferred working alone, a signal of the rising demand for autonomy in the workplace. This trend is expected to continue, particularly as Generation Z will make up 35% of the workforce by 2025, overtaking millennials.

ABC Corporation, a prominent manufacturing company in the Philippines, operated under high production standards while striving to maintain a motivated workforce. As a large-scale manufacturer of trucks and buses, it required stringent oversight to ensure that production tasks met precise organizational standards and quality expectations. However, excessive managerial control negatively affected Generation Z employees, decreasing job satisfaction, increasing burnout, and higher employee turnover. As noted in recent studies, Filipino Gen Z workers responded poorly to restrictive management practices that limited their autonomy and professional growth. This generation valued meaningful work and opportunities for career advancement, and when these expectations were unmet, they often sought employment elsewhere.

This study examined the implications of micromanagement on Generation Z production employees at ABC Corporation, analyzing the effects of managerial control and decision-making autonomy on job performance. It contributed to the growing discourse on leadership styles and workforce engagement, offering evidence-based recommendations for balancing oversight and independence to enhance retention, motivation, and productivity. Additionally, the research explored generational preferences in workplace management, highlighting the benefits of adaptive and collaborative leadership styles in improving engagement and retention. As competition in the manufacturing sector intensified, optimizing leadership approaches for younger employees became necessary, providing valuable insights for ABC Corporation and similar organizations seeking to align management strategies with Gen Z expectations.

Research Questions

This study aimed to investigate how micromanagement influenced the performance of Generation Z production employees at ABC Corporation, examining its effects on different aspects of their effectiveness in their roles. Specifically, the study aimed to answer the following questions:

1. What is the manifestation level of micromanagement leadership style as perceived by the Generation Z production employees at ABC Corporation in terms of:
 - 1.1 Managerial Control, and
 - 1.2 Decision-Making Autonomy?
2. What is the job performance level of Generation Z production employees at ABC Corporation in terms of:
 - 2.1 Work Efficiency and Productivity; and

2.2 Employee Motivation and Engagement?

3. Is there a significant relationship between the level of manifestation of micromanagement leadership style and the performance level of Generation Z production employees at ABC Corporation?

4. Based on the findings of the study, what action plan can be proposed?

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

This research employed a descriptive correlational research design to examine the relationship between the perceived micromanagement leadership style practices and employee performance among Generation Z production employees at ABC Corporation. Descriptive research provided an overview of the current micromanagement leadership style as perceived by Generation Z employees in the production. This approach helps analyze the existing conditions and the implications for the workers. Correlational research compared micromanagement leadership style to employee performance. To understand the interconnection of the variables in the study, the study aimed to identify patterns and forecast trends based on the data gathered.

To ensure the research aligned with established methodologies in the field, the design adhered to Creswell and Creswell (2023) procedure, which involved both descriptive and correlational research. This procedure emphasized the importance of clearly and consistently defining the research approach in line with the study's objectives. This approach made the collected data credible and relevant for identifying and understanding the tendencies and relationships between micromanagement and employee performance.

Locale

The study was conducted at ABC Corporation, a manufacturing company located in Calamba, Laguna, Philippines, which assembles and distributes trucks and buses. As noted in the scope and delimitations, the company's real name is withheld to maintain privacy and confidentiality.

ABC Corporation was selected as the research site due to its prominence in the competitive manufacturing sector, where work efficiency, productivity, employee motivation, and engagement are crucial. This makes it an ideal setting to explore the effects of micromanagement on employee performance.

Lastly, the company's structure and strategic importance make the findings applicable beyond the organization itself, potentially benefiting other firms seeking to enhance productivity while supporting employee well-being.

Population and Sampling

The study involved 120 respondents from 602 production employees, including the production area and the production office. In this research, stratified random sampling was employed. The number of respondents was calculated through G*power 3.1.9, with a power of 95%. This approach ensured that the study had a strong design.

The population involved production employees from ABC Corporation who belong to Generation Z since they are principally engaged in the production activities. These employees are very critical in production, and as such, they are the first account holders of the micromanagement practices that were investigated.

Respondents of the Study

The study involved 120 Generation Z production employees, selected through stratified random sampling to ensure proportional representation across different work areas. The Generation Z production employees working within the production line and the production office at ABC Corporation were included. These roles comprised the Chassis Assembly Line, Structural Line, Painting Section, Trimming Line, Pre-delivery Inspection, and various production office positions.

Table A
Distribution of the Respondents

Category	Population	Frequency	Percent
Production Lines	42	40	33%
Production Office	84	80	66%
Total	126	120	100%

As shown in the table above, the production department was divided into two strata: Production Lines and Production Office, with respective populations of 42 and 84 Generation Z employees. Stratified random sampling was applied to ensure that each subgroup was proportionally represented in the study.

Instrument

This study utilized an adopted questionnaire as the primary data collection tool, ensuring that the measurement of micromanagement and employee performance was based on a structured and validated instrument. The questionnaire was adopted from the study "*Micromanagement on Employee Performance: A Killer or Motivator*" by Galindez et al. (2024), which was designed to assess the relationship between micromanagement and employee performance in an organizational setting. Using an established instrument strengthened the validity and reliability of the collected data, as it had already been tested for consistency and relevance in a similar research context.

The questionnaire consisted of two sections. The first section measured employees' perceptions of micromanagement in the workplace, specifically regarding managerial control and decision-making autonomy. This section aimed to identify how often respondents experienced micromanagement practices, such as close supervision, lack of trust, and limited involvement in decision-making. These indicators are vital for understanding how micromanagement exists within the organization and how it affects employees' sense of control and independence at work.

The second section evaluated employee performance in terms of work efficiency, productivity, motivation, and engagement. Items in this section were designed to capture how micromanagement influenced key performance metrics, including output quality, task completion, problem-solving, and the willingness of employees to go beyond minimum expectations. Additionally, it explored the emotional and psychological aspects of performance, such as job satisfaction, motivation levels, and enthusiasm for tasks.

Each item in the questionnaire used a five-point Likert scale ranging from "Strongly Disagree" to "Strongly Agree," allowing for a nuanced understanding of participant responses. The scale enabled quantifiable analysis of patterns and relationships between variables, contributing to the robustness of the study's findings.

Responses were collected using a 4-point Likert scale, maintaining the same structure and interpretation as the original study to ensure consistency in data measurement. The Likert scale ranged from "Strongly Disagree" to "Strongly Agree," allowing respondents to express varying degrees of agreement with each statement. Moreover, the simplicity of the 4-point rating scale is as follows:

Scale for Workplace Perception of Micromanagement Leadership Style*

Range	Rating	Categorical Response	Verbal Interpretation
3.26 - 4.00	4	Strongly Agree	Highly Observed
2.51 - 3.25	3	Agree	Observed
1.76 - 2.50	2	Disagree	Slightly Observed
1.00 - 1.75	1	Strongly Disagree	Not Observed

**Arbitrary Scale for the Perceived Manifestation Level of Micromanagement Leadership Style as Perceived by Generation Z Production Employees at ABC Corporation*

Scale for Generation Z Performance Under Micromanagement*

Range	Rating	Categorical Response	Verbal Interpretation
3.26 - 4.00	4	Strongly Agree	Very Good

2.51 - 3.25	3	Agree	Good
1.76 - 2.50	2	Disagree	Fair
1.00 - 1.75	1	Strongly Disagree	Poor

**Arbitrary Scale for the Level of Employee Performance among Generation Z Production Employees at ABC Corporation.*

Validation of Instrument

This study utilized an adopted questionnaire from the research “*Micromanagement on Employee Performance: A Killer or Motivator*” by Galindez et al. (2024). The instrument was initially developed and validated in their study to measure the relationship between micromanagement and employee performance. It was structured to ensure clarity, reliability, and consistency in assessing employees' experiences with micromanagement and their perceived performance in the workplace.

This study employed the same questionnaire, with all indicators retained, to uphold methodological rigor and ensure alignment with established frameworks. Cronbach’s Alpha reliability coefficients were referenced to assess the instrument’s internal consistency. All indicators under both the independent variable (Perceived Level of Manifestation of Micromanagement) and the dependent variable (Performance Level of Generation Z Employees) recorded Cronbach’s Alpha values greater than 0.85, indicating high internal reliability.

Data Gathering Procedure

After the research proposal was approved, a formal letter was sent to ABC Corporation's management requesting permission to conduct the study on micromanagement effectiveness and employee performance among Generation Z production employees. The approval was granted. The adopted questionnaire was then administered to the identified respondents and distributed within a set timeline to ensure a smooth data collection process.

To ensure that participants fully understood the aims and objectives of the research, they were provided with a detailed letter accompanying the questionnaire. This letter explained all aspects of the study, including its objectives, scope, and the measures taken to maintain participant privacy and anonymity. Respondents were given a specific deadline to complete the questionnaire, and follow-ups were made regularly to ensure a high response rate. The respondents' cooperation and willingness significantly contributed to the timely and efficient data collection. Once all completed questionnaires were collected, the data were sorted, coded, and tallied in preparation for analysis. A statistician was employed to assist with analyzing and interpreting the data. The results derived from this process served as the basis for addressing the research questions and formulating the study’s conclusions and recommendations.

Treatment of Quantitative Data

The following statistical treatments were applied to analyze the data gathered in the study. These were processed by a statistician using the Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS):

1. Mean and the Four-Point Likert Scale were used to describe both the extent to which micromanagement was experienced and the level of employee performance among Generation Z production employees at ABC Corporation, following the original interpretation framework of the adopted questionnaire.

2. Pearson Correlation Analysis was applied to examine the relationship between micromanagement and employee performance among Generation Z production employees at ABC Corporation. This method determined the strength and direction of the relationship between managerial control, decision-making autonomy, and employee performance based on computed correlation values and significance levels. The results guided the interpretation of how micromanagement influences work efficiency, productivity, motivation, and engagement without establishing predictive causation.

RESULTS

Research Question Number 1. What is the manifestation level of micromanagement leadership style as perceived by the Generation Z production employees at ABC Corporation in terms of Managerial Control and Decision-Making Autonomy?

Table 1.1

Manifestation Level of Micromanagement Leadership Style as perceived by the Generation Z Production Employees at ABC Corporation in terms of Managerial Control

Indicators	\bar{X}	VI	Rank
1. My manager controls most of my work.	2.35	PM	5
2. I have to provide my manager with frequent updates about my tasks.	2.78	M	2
3. My manager always oversees even the most minor details of my tasks.	2.54	M	3
4. I receive a lot of unsolicited advice about my work from my manager.	2.37	PM	4
5. My work is not open to new developments or approaches.	2.79	M	1
GENERAL ASSESSMENT	2.57	M	
Standard deviation	0.984		

Legend: 3.25 – 4.00 Highly Observed/ Fully Manifested (FM)
2.50 – 3.24 Observed/ Manifested (M)

1.75 – 2.49 Slightly Observed/ Partially Manifested (PM)
1.00 – 1.74 Not Observed/ Not Manifested (NM)

Table 1.2

Manifestation Level of Micromanagement Leadership Style as perceived by the Generation Z Production Employees at ABC Corporation in terms of Decision-Making Autonomy

Indicators	\bar{X}	VI	Rank
1. I don't make individual decisions at the workplace all the time.	2.71	M	3
2. My manager does not trust my decisions in the workplace.	2.25	PM	5
3. I don't often express my individuality and creativity at work.	2.83	M	2
4. My work environment is stressful to me.	2.35	PM	4
5. I don't have lot of opportunities to take lead in projects.	2.87	M	1
GENERAL ASSESSMENT	2.60	M	
Standard Deviation	0.768		

Legend: 3.25 – 4.00 Highly Observed/ Fully Manifested (FM) 1.75 – 2.49 Slightly Observed/ Partially Manifested (PM)
 2.50 – 3.24 Observed/ Manifested (M) 1.00 – 1.74 Not Observed/ Not Manifested (NM)

Research Question Number 2. What is the performance level of Generation Z production employees at ABC Corporation in terms of Work Efficiency and Productivity and Employee Motivation and Engagement?

Table 2.1

Job Performance Level of Generation Z Production Employees at ABC Corporation in terms of Work Efficiency and Productivity

Indicators	\bar{X}	VI	Rank
1. I feel confident in my ability to perform my job tasks efficiently.	2.63	G	2
2. I effectively manage my time to complete tasks by their deadlines.	2.58	G	3
3. I demonstrate a high level of accuracy and attention to detail in my work.	2.48	F	5
4. I consistently meet or exceed the goals and objectives set for my role.	2.49	F	4
5. I am proactive in solving problems and seeking solutions.	2.89	G	1
GENERAL ASSESSMENT	2.61	G	
Standard Deviation	0.813		

Legend: 3.25 – 4.00 Very Good (VG) 1.75 – 2.49 Fair (F)
 2.50 – 3.24 Good (G) 1.00 – 1.74 Poor (P)

Table 2.2**Job Performance Level of Generation Z Production Employees at ABC Corporation in terms of Employee Motivation and Engagement**

Indicators	\bar{X}	VI	Rank
1. I am satisfied with the quality of my work.	2.74	G	4
2. I adapt well to changes in the workplace and new challenges.	2.68	G	5
3. I collaborate well with team members to achieve common goals.	2.94	G	2
4. I am motivated to perform better at tasks.	3.01	G	1
5. I take initiative to go beyond my job responsibilities when needed.	2.87	G	3
GENERAL ASSESSMENT	2.85	G	
Standard Deviation	0.611		

Legend: 3.25 – 4.00 Very Good (VG)
2.50 – 3.24 Good (G)

1.75 – 2.49 Fair (F)
1.00 – 1.74 Poor (P)

Research Question Number 3. Is there a significant relationship between the level of manifestation of micromanagement leadership style and the performance level of Generation Z production employees in ABC Corporation?

Table 3**Test of Significant Relationship between the Level of Manifestation of Micromanagement Leadership Style and the Performance Level of Generation Z Production Employees at ABC Corporation**

Level of Manifestation of Micromanagement Leadership Style	Performance Level of Generation Z Production Employees	r value	p value	Remarks	Decision
Managerial Control	Work Efficiency and Productivity	.189*	.039	Significant	Reject H_0
	Employee Motivation and Engagement	.180*	.049	Significant	Reject H_0
Decision-Making Autonomy	Work Efficiency and Productivity	-.074	.420	Not Significant	Accept H_0
	Employee Motivation and Engagement	-.135	.141	Not Significant	Accept H_0

**Correlational at the level 0.01

*Correlational at the level 0.05(Two-tailed)

Research Question Number 4. Based on the findings of the study, what action plan can be proposed?

Table 4
Proposed Action Plan

Key/ Areas	Objectives	Strategies/ Activities	Persons Involved	Success Indicators
Managerial Control	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Encourage openness to new ideas and reduce excessive supervision to enhance flexibility and innovation. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Conduct leadership training focused on delegation and openness to innovation; implement a feedback system for suggestions. 	Managers, Team Leaders – Apply training and gather suggestions. HR Department – Provide training and monitor trends	30% reduction in complaints on excessive control; 20% of process improvements sourced from employee suggestions
Decision- Making Autonomy	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Promote initiative and strengthen employee involvement in workplace decisions. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Implement mentorship and flexible work arrangements to support independent problem solving; establish a recognition system for initiative. 	HR Department – Manage programs and rewards. Managers – Support autonomy and identify proactive employees	25% increase in employees leading projects; 20% rise in formal recognition for independent decision-making
Work Efficiency and Productivity	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Improve employee accuracy and attention to detail in daily tasks 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Provide focused workshops on quality standards and task management; offer regular feedback and peer-review sessions 	Department Heads – Monitor and support quality efforts HR – Organize workshops	15% improvement in accuracy and error reduction as noted in quality control or performance reports

Employee Motivation and Engagement	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Strengthen adaptability and resilience to workplace changes and new challenges. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Initiate cross-training and adaptation activities to expose employees to different tasks; provide coaching on change management. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> HR – Lead adaptation programs Supervisors – Offer coaching and feedback during transitions 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 20% increase in self-rated adaptability scores; reduced resistance to change based on supervisor feedback
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DISCUSSION

Research Question Number 1. What is the manifestation level of micromanagement leadership style as perceived by the Generation Z production employees at ABC Corporation in terms of Managerial Control and Decision-Making Autonomy?

The micromanagement leadership style, as perceived by the Generation Z production employees at XYZ Corporation, in terms of managerial control, was “**Manifested**”, with a general assessment of **2.57**, as shown in Table 1.1. Almost all indicators were verbally interpreted as “Manifested.” The indicator “My work is not open to new developments or approaches” had the highest mean score of **2.79**, interpreted as “Manifested”. Meanwhile, the indicator “My manager controls most of my work” had the lowest computed mean of **2.35**, interpreted as “Partially Manifested”. This implies that managerial control is actively present in the workplace but is not consistently applied to all aspects of employee tasks. Employees perceive a structured environment with limited space for innovation, yet there are still areas where they are allowed to exercise independence. The results reflect a leadership approach that enforces control while cautiously allowing limited autonomy depending on the situation. This is supported by Khoury and Tannous (2020), who emphasized that structured management environments often suppress innovation, limiting employees’ ability to respond to dynamic work conditions. Their study concluded that a balanced approach is essential to sustain control and creative thinking. Furthermore, Ryan and Cross (2023) found that micromanagement does not have a uniform effect across all areas of work. When managers ease control in selected areas, employees are more likely to feel engaged and make effective decisions, contributing to better team performance. In addition, Ramos and Malangen (2023) explained that while managerial oversight is crucial for maintaining order and compliance, too much control can lead to workplace dissatisfaction. Their research advocates for a balance between authority and autonomy to promote discipline and employee morale. Additionally, Fleeton (2024) noted that when employees are given space for self-management, they develop a stronger sense of ownership and responsibility. He warned that excessive micromanagement erodes trust and diminishes intrinsic motivation, which are critical for sustained productivity.

The micromanagement leadership style, as perceived by the Generation Z production employees at XYZ Corporation, in terms of Decision-Making Autonomy, was **“Manifested”**, with a general assessment of **2.60**, as shown in Table 1.1. Almost all indicators were verbally interpreted as “Manifested.” The indicator “I don’t have lot of opportunities to take lead in projects” had the highest mean score of **2.87**, interpreted as Manifested. Meanwhile, the indicator “My work environment is stressful to me” had the lowest computed mean of **2.35**, interpreted as “Partially Manifested”. This implies that decision-making autonomy exists at ABC Corporation, but it is not fully embedded in the organizational culture. Employees are allowed some freedom in decisions, but often encounter barriers when attempting to lead or propose changes. The constraints point to a micromanagement tendency where control is prioritized over empowerment, and initiative is not consistently encouraged. This is supported by Ichsan et al. (2021), who emphasized that decision-making autonomy enhances employee efficiency and encourages proactive behavior. Their research found that when workers are empowered to take initiative, they develop stronger problem-solving abilities and make more significant contributions to organizational success. The lack of such opportunities in ABC Corporation may limit engagement and innovative capacity. Additionally, Fleeton (2024) explained that trust is a critical foundation for autonomy. Without it, employees may avoid making decisions due to fear of disapproval or reversal. His findings stress that when managers demonstrate trust, it fosters accountability, reduces the need for supervision, and boosts performance across teams. On the top of that, Bans-Akutey (2020) noted that limited autonomy negatively affects adaptability and decision-making under pressure. His study concluded that organizations that fail to empower employees risk reduced productivity, lowered morale, and weaker problem-solving capacities, which can compromise long-term success.

Research Question Number 2. What is the performance level of Generation Z production employees at ABC Corporation in terms of Work Efficiency and Productivity and Employee Motivation and Engagement?

The job performance level of Generation Z production employees at ABC Corporation in terms of work efficiency and productivity was **“Good”**, with a general assessment of **2.61**, as shown in Table 2.1. Almost all indicators were verbally interpreted as “Good.” The indicator “I am proactive in solving problems and seeking solutions” had the highest mean score of **2.89**, interpreted as “Good”. In contrast, the indicator “I demonstrate a high level of accuracy and attention to detail in my work” had the lowest mean score of **2.48**, interpreted as “Fair”. This indicates that Generation Z employees are generally productive and efficient, capable of fulfilling their responsibilities effectively. However, tasks requiring meticulous attention need improvement, indicating the need for balanced development in initiative and detail orientation. This was supported by Ichsan et al. (2021) supported the importance of employee proactiveness, asserting that decision-making autonomy leads to more effective problem-solving and enhanced productivity. Their study concluded that when employees are trusted to take initiative, their contribution to operational success improves significantly. Similarly, Willford (2023) emphasized that cultivating a workplace environment that values innovation and independent thinking boosts employee performance. His findings highlighted that

employees perform better when they are empowered to actively engage with challenges rather than passively follow instructions, resulting in improved overall efficiency. Enyinna et al. (2024) also found that motivation plays a crucial role in promoting accuracy and high-quality work. Their research showed that motivated employees are more attentive to details, improving the precision of their output and contributing to overall organizational excellence. On the top of that, Bans-Akutey (2020) warned that excessive control can diminish employee initiative and indirectly affect their attention to detail. According to the study, overly monitored environments may cause disengagement, which negatively influences the quality of work and the ability to self-correct errors. Furthermore, Bakker (2020) explained that Generation Z employees thrive in environments where they are provided with meaningful tasks and opportunities for skill development. His study found that engagement and productivity are closely linked, and young professionals perform best when their work aligns with personal and career growth goals. In addition, Demirbilek and Keser (2022) found that leadership styles emphasizing flexibility and collaboration have a positive effect on productivity. Their research showed that employees become more efficient when encouraged to communicate openly and contribute actively to the organization's objectives.

The job performance level of Generation Z production employees at ABC Corporation, in terms of employee motivation and engagement, was “**Good**”, with a general assessment of **2.85**, as shown in Table 2.1. All indicators were verbally interpreted as “Good.” The indicator “I am motivated to perform better at tasks” had the highest mean score of **3.01**, interpreted as Good. In contrast, the indicator “I adapt well to changes in the workplace and new challenges” had the lowest mean score of **2.68**, interpreted as “Good”. These results indicate that Generation Z employees are generally motivated and engaged in their responsibilities. However, efforts should be made to fully harness their potential to improve resilience and support mechanisms for handling workplace change. This was supported by Enyinna et al. (2024), who highlighted the connection between motivation and performance, highlighting that intrinsically driven employees are more productive and committed to their tasks. Their study concluded that motivation significantly improves workplace engagement and output quality. Additionally, Bakker (2020) found that Generation Z workers thrive when their roles are aligned with meaningful tasks and opportunities for growth. According to the study, career development is a major driver of sustained motivation, making professional advancement initiatives essential for maintaining engagement. On the top of that, Othman et al. (2024) emphasized that adapting to change can be challenging for younger employees, especially when expectations are unclear. Their research showed that clear communication and structured guidance ease transitions and improve adaptability in dynamic work environments. Also, Zhu et al. (2024) added that emotional and cognitive support play a vital role in enhancing employee resilience. Their findings revealed that workplaces that prioritize mental wellness and clarity during transitions maintain stronger engagement levels among their employees. Additionally, Fleeton (2024) emphasized the importance of autonomy in enhancing motivation. His study found that employees perform best when they are trusted to work independently, and that this trust fosters higher levels of commitment and participation in organizational goals. Furthermore, Benítez-Márquez et al. (2022) found that flexibility and recognition are key expectations for Generation Z.

Organizations that tailor leadership approaches to meet these expectations report increased levels of employee satisfaction and loyalty. Also, Febriana and Mujib (2024) focused on the impact of autonomy on motivation, concluding that when employees are empowered to contribute their ideas and take ownership of their roles, they demonstrate greater enthusiasm and initiative at work. Furthermore, Byrd-Bredbenner (2020) pointed out that digital communication tools positively influence engagement. According to the study, Generation Z values frequent feedback and interactive collaboration, which enhance their connection to their work and improve job satisfaction. These findings underscore the importance of cultivating a work environment that promotes autonomy, trust, and adaptability to support sustained motivation and engagement among Generation Z employees.

Research Question Number 3. Is there a significant relationship between the level of manifestation of micromanagement leadership style and the performance level of Generation Z production employees in ABC Corporation?

The level of manifestation of micromanagement leadership style and the performance of Generation Z production employees at ABC Corporation showed mixed results in terms of a test of significant relationship, as shown in Table 3. Micromanagement in managerial control demonstrated a significant inverse relationship with employee performance, with corresponding p-values of **0.039 and 0.049**, putting them both below the 0.05 significance level. On the other hand, in terms of decision-making autonomy, micromanagement showed no significant relationship with employee performance, as indicated by higher p-values, **0.420 and 0.141**, leading to the acceptance of the null hypothesis. The r-values ranging from **-0.180 to -0.189** were interpreted as very low negative correlations, indicating an inverse relationship between the level of manifestation of micromanagement in terms of Managerial Control and the performance level of Generation Z production employees. The computed probability values **0.039 and 0.049** were less than the level of significance ($p < 0.05$); thus, the null hypothesis is rejected. It implies that the higher the levels of managerial control are, the lower the levels of work efficiency, productivity, motivation, and engagement among Generation Z production employees. On the other hand, when it comes to decision-making autonomy, the extent to which employees are allowed or restricted in decision-making does not significantly affect their performance in this organizational context. To further explain, Table 3 tests the significant relationship between the level of manifestation of micromanagement leadership style and the performance level of Generation Z production employees at ABC Corporation. To simplify, the findings imply that the level of manifestation of micromanagement leadership style in terms of Managerial Control has a significant inverse relationship with the performance level of Generation Z production employees at ABC Corporation. This means that the higher the level of micromanagement in terms of Managerial Control, the lower the performance level of Generation Z production employees. On the other hand, for Decision-Making Autonomy, this aspect of micromanagement may not be as influential on performance outcomes for Gen Z employees, at least not in ABC corporation's production setting. Overall, while the correlation between managerial control and performance is weak, its significance suggests that micromanagement strategies affect workplace dynamics. The relationship

observed in this study supports literature emphasizing the importance of autonomy and balanced leadership in optimizing employee efficiency and engagement. The finding aligns with the study of Kamarudin et al. (2023), which highlighted that excessive managerial control leads employees to develop protective behaviors, slowing down work routines and reducing overall productivity. Their research suggests that persistent monitoring limits creativity and workplace efficiency, supporting that micromanagement may hinder employees' optimal performance levels. Similarly, Ryan and Cross (2023) explained that micromanagement emerged as a preventive measure when leaders feel the need for increased supervision. However, their findings indicated that heightened control can restrict employee autonomy, affecting engagement and overall job satisfaction. The results of their study suggest that employees might respond negatively to excessive control, as it impacts their ability to perform independently. Moreover, Fleeton (2024) emphasized that trust-based leadership and decision-making autonomy contributed to greater workplace motivation and improved performance. This supports the interpretation that micromanagement, particularly in managerial control, may create barriers that lower efficiency and engagement among employees. Organizations must consider striking a balance between oversight and independence to mitigate the adverse effects of micromanagement. Additionally, Bans-Akutey (2020) stressed that restricted autonomy in decision-making creates resistance against organizational changes and disrupts employee development. Their findings indicate that while managerial control is observed, its level of manifestation influences the performance of employees. Ensuring flexibility in managerial approaches may help counteract potential negative effects.

Research Question Number 4. Based on the findings of the study, what action plan can be proposed?

Micromanagement has long been recognized as a leadership style that, when excessively applied, can hinder employee autonomy and workplace efficiency. Based on the findings of this study, Generation Z production employees at ABC Corporation experience notable levels of managerial control, which impacts their ability to take initiative and adapt to workplace changes. While employees generally exhibit good productivity and motivation, the restrictive nature of micromanagement in certain areas affects engagement and performance. Based on the study's findings, specific areas were identified that require targeted interventions to enhance the overall performance and satisfaction of Generation Z production employees.

Conclusions

Based on the findings of the study, the following conclusions may be derived:

1. That the managerial control is actively present in the workplace but is not consistently applied to all aspects of employee tasks. Employees perceive a structured environment with limited space for innovation, yet there are still areas where they are allowed to exercise independence. The results reflect a leadership approach that enforces control while cautiously allowing limited autonomy depending on the situation. That the decision-making autonomy exists at ABC Corporation, but it is not fully

embedded in the organizational culture. Employees are allowed some freedom in decisions, but often encounter barriers when attempting to lead or propose changes. The constraints point to a micromanagement tendency where control is prioritized over empowerment, and initiative is not consistently encouraged.

2. That Generation Z employees are generally productive and efficient, capable of fulfilling their responsibilities effectively. However, tasks requiring meticulous attention need improvement, indicating the need for balanced development in initiative and detail orientation. That Generation Z employees are generally motivated and engaged in their responsibilities. However, efforts should be made to fully harness their potential to improve resilience and support mechanisms for handling workplace change.

3. That the level of manifestation of micromanagement leadership style in terms of Managerial Control has a significant inverse relationship with the performance level of Generation Z production employees at ABC Corporation. This means that the higher the level of micromanagement in terms of Managerial Control, the lower the performance level of Generation Z production employees.

4. That an action plan was proposed to ABC Corporation in Calamba, Laguna. It aims to enhance managerial control and decision-making autonomy to improve the performance of Generation Z production employees. This action plan outlines strategies such as trust-building leadership training, structured feedback systems, and clearer delegation of responsibilities. These initiatives are intended to strengthen employee productivity, job satisfaction, and overall workplace efficiency.

Recommendations

Considering the findings and conclusions, the following recommendations aim to address the challenges observed in the manifestation of micromanagement leadership style and its effects on the performance of Generation Z production employees at ABC Corporation. These actionable suggestions may enhance workplace efficiency, motivation, and adaptability while fostering a balanced leadership approach.

1. The company may allow greater flexibility in work methods, encouraging innovation while maintaining structured oversight. Managers may also refine leadership strategies to ensure employees have opportunities to explore new solutions without excessive supervision.

2. The company may implement targeted training programs focusing on quality assurance, ensuring employees improve their attention to detail in their work. By reinforcing these areas, the company may sustain high engagement and efficiency levels among its workforce while ensuring greater accuracy and effectiveness in task execution.

3. The company may recalibrate managerial control to emphasize trust-based leadership, where employees feel empowered rather than restricted. Strengthening feedback mechanisms may help employees voice concerns about managerial oversight, allowing leaders to adjust supervision approaches based on workplace needs. By promoting autonomy in operational areas, ABC Corporation may create a healthier work environment that encourages engagement and efficiency.

4. The company may consider implementing the action plan proposed in this study, which provides structured strategies for balancing oversight and employee

independence. These strategies, including trust-building leadership training, flexible work arrangements, and feedback-driven improvements, may help refine existing management practices. Regular assessments using employee surveys and performance tracking may ensure that implemented strategies are effective and aligned with corporate objectives.

5. Future researchers may explore the long-term impacts of micromanagement leadership style on other generational cohorts in the workplace, such as Millennials or Generation X. Additionally, they may investigate how micromanagement interacts with cultural differences in global organizational settings. Expanding the scope of the research to include diverse industries and leadership styles may also offer insights into creating a balanced and innovative work environment.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

Ethical considerations were strictly observed throughout the research process, as the participation of Generation Z production employees involved sensitive and personal data. The study prioritized securing informed consent from all respondents by clearly explaining the research's purpose, scope, and objectives before their participation. Respondents were assured of their anonymity and the confidentiality of their responses. The data collected was protected under strict guidelines and used solely for research purposes. Transparency in communication was maintained to ensure participants fully understood their role and that the ethical measures were in place. All participants were treated fairly and respectfully, and only information necessary to address the research questions was gathered.

In compliance with the Data Privacy Act of 2012, all participant information collected was protected regarding their rights. The researcher maintained the collected data's anonymity, security, and restricted access. Participants were informed of their rights under the Data Privacy Act, including their right to withdraw from the study without penalty.

Clear and consistent communication was upheld to ensure participants were informed of their role, the ethical practices to protect their data, and how their information would be used. Participants were treated fairly and respectfully, and only data relevant to the research questions was collected, adhering to the principle of data minimization. Confidentiality was maintained throughout the entire research process.

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